

Table continued.

Designation	Cross	Source of resistance against		
		Biotype 1	Biotypes 1 and 4	
IET12523 IET12524 IET12525	RP2231 selections	Phalguna/ Velluthacheera	Siam 29	Velluthacheera
IET10762 IET11470 -	RP2432-68-11-9 RP1607-1240-42 RP2434-45-3-2	IR36/IET7916 Phalguna/MR1523 IR50/IET7918	Siam 29 Siam 29 Siam 29	Ptb18, Ptb21 Ptb18, Ptb21 Ptb18, Ptb21
IET10891 IET12871	RP2235-179-16-10 WGL 46753	Phalguna/IR50 Surekha/WGL 16145	Siam 29 Siam 29, Eswarakora	Ptb18, Ptb21 -
IET10850 IET10851	R321 selections	Samridhi/IR36	Eswarakora	Ptb18, Ptb21
IET10517 IET10314 IET10312 IET10313	CR401-6-1 WR6-120-10 CR380 selections	Vijaya/CR904 IR62/Parmel CRII/Ratna		? ? ?
IET10407 IET12349 -	TNAU801790 CR30-20-1 RR217-1	CR41/CO 39 IR8/Sigadis IR17491-5-4-3/ IR2415-90-4-3// IR9129-209-2-2		? ? ?

test was used under greenhouse conditions from 1988 to 1990, and replicated four times. Sixty cultures were found resistant to both biotypes (see table). None of the biotype 4-resistant cultures were susceptible to biotype 1, but all of the cultures susceptible to biotype 1 were also susceptible to biotype 4.

Resistance to both biotypes was contributed mainly to the lines by Orumundakan, Velluthacheera, Ptb10, Ptb21, and combinations of two or more donors. Nine cultures exhibiting resistance were derivatives of Siam 29, which is, like its derivative Phalguna, resistant to biotype 1 but susceptible to biotype 4. The other parents involved in cross combinations with Siam 29 and its derivatives probably contributed or modified the resistance reaction in these cultures.

Further studies on reactions of parents involved in these crosses might identify additional gene sources for resistance. ■

Pest resistance— insects

Brown planthopper (BPH)- resistant cultivars from Madhya Pradesh Rice Research Institute (MPRRI) germplasm

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Host plant resistance is an important component of pest management programs to control *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål. To stay ahead of the emergence of new insect biotypes, improved resistant cultivars with more genetic diversity must be developed.

We evaluated 900 MPRRI rice cultivars during 1990-92 to locate better sources of BPH resistance. We infested 9- to 10-d-old test seedlings and checks TN1 and Ptb33 with 1st- and 2d-instar BPH nymphs. Damage to seedlings was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (0-9) scale. Cultivars scoring less than three were retested three to six times. Sixty-nine cultivars were

BPH-resistant cultivars from MPRRI germplasm.

Cultivar	IGKV Acc. no.	Av plant damage score ^a (0-9 scale)	District of origin	Cultivar	IGKV Acc. no.	Av plant damage score ^a (0-9 scale)	District of origin
Kakadi	K:2531	1.9	Bastar	Kakadiha	K:1832	1.6	Raipur
Chhoti Kanhai	C:758	2.9	Bastar	Kali Kamod	K:224	2.4	Raipur
Kanhaiya	K:2167	2.9	Bastar	Kanthgulas	K:711 III	2.5	Raipur
Dodki	D:1015	1.2	Bastar	Bhatha Dhouri	B:2876	1.1	Raipur
Farsa Phool	F:16	0.1	Bastar	Dhumki	D:1114	1.5	Raipur
Bhata-Gada-Khuta	B:803 II	2.3	Bastar	Dokalam	D:279	1.1	Raipur
Gada Khota	G:978	1.7	Bastar	Kankadiya	K:1699	2.9	Raigarh
Hinga	H:435	0.7	Bastar	Dokalam	D:455 III	2.0	Raipur
Jalki	J:287III	1.3	Bastar	Hathi Panjada	H:218	0.2	Raipur
Kabari	K:2312	2.8	Bastar	Hasa	H:56	2.4	Raipur
Kabari	K:2388	2.5	Bastar	Jagnath	J:55 II	2.1	Raipur
Kanhaiya	K:2413	2.3	Bastar	Prasad			
Kappe	K:1592	2.3	Bastar	Jaybay Rang	J:432	0.0	Raipur
Bas Bhira	B:2655	2.6	Bastar	Karhani	K:556 II	1.7	Raipur
Barangi	B:1862	1.3	Bastar	Karhani	K:1173	1.7	Raipur
Basangi	B:2682	0.6	Bastar	Khatia Pati	K:60	1.9	Raipur
Bhainspath	B:61 I	2.0	Bastar	Kalam	K:1167 I	2.7	Sarguja
Kalamdani	K:2478	1.8	Raigarh	Kalamdani	K:1163	2.6	Sarguja
Kankadiya	K:430	1.6	Raigarh	Dhouri	D:8011	3.0	Sarguja
Kandradiya	K:446 II	1.5	Raigarh	Karhani	K:1911	2.6	Sarguja
Dokalam	D:455 II	1.5	Raipur	Kanai	K:1885	2.4	Bilaspur
Dhouri	D:1043	0.7	Raigarh	Khondharo			
Dhouri	D:1163	2.0	Raigarh	Kanak	K:1741	2.4	Bilaspur
Dhouri	D:1167	2.0	Raigarh	Kankadiya	K:652	2.4	Bilaspur
Bhatha Dhouri	B:1651	1.6	Raigarh	Kapursar	K:1798	2.7	Bilaspur
Gang Puriha	G:809	2.0	Raigarh	Karapari	K:164	2.3	Bilaspur
Dahi Barhi	D:1771	2.0	Raigarh	Dhori Sulti	D:1070	1.9	Bilaspur
				Ganga Prasad	G:760	3.0	Bilaspur

continued on next page

Cultivar	IGKV Acc. no.	Av plant damage score ^a (0-9 scale)	District of origin	Cultivar	IGKV Acc. no.	Av plant damage score ^a (0-9 scale)	District of origin
Gopal Prasad	G:778 II	1.8	Bilaspur	Kanak	K:1741	2.4	Shahdol
Girmit	G:570	1.7	Balaghat	Barhi	B:1253 I	2.2	Mandla
Girmit	G:572	2.7	Balaghat	Barhi	B:1253 II	2.5	Mandla
Kansari	K:1761	1.1	Sidhi	Hiranakhi	H:161	2.8	Mandla
Galra	G:718	2.5	Sidhi	Basmati	B:409	2.6	Hoshangabad
Gadur Sela	G:699	0.6	Rajnandgaon	Wasmati	W:9 I	0.6	Muraina
Gadur Sela	G:701	2.9	Rajnandgaon	Kakadisar	K:544	2.8	Seoni
Ganja Kali	G:702	2.2	Rajnandgaon	TN1 (susceptible check)		9.0	
Kari Barhi	K:666	2.8	Rajnandgaon	Ptb33 (resistant check)		1.8	

^aBased on SES.

found resistant to BPH (see table). Most of them are from Bastar and Raipur districts. Results indicate that the germplasm maintained at MPRRI (about

Stress tolerance— excess water

Amount of volatile aldehydes released by rice plants after submergence

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During the initial phase of rice seed germination, the production of volatile aldehydes is significantly lower in high-vigor seeds than in medium- and low-vigor seeds.

We conducted an experiment to learn if a relationship exists between plant volatile aldehyde production and submergence tolerance. Seedlings of 10 rice varieties (see table) with varying degrees of submergence tolerance based on seedling survival were grown under greenhouse conditions. At 70 d after seeding, they were completely submerged for 6 d.

To determine aldehyde production, a 50-ml beaker containing 10 ml of 0.2% (wt/vol) 3-methyl-2-benzothiazolinone-hydrozone (MBTH) was placed inside a larger bottle containing a 5-g sample of chopped tissues from nonsubmerged and submerged plants. Each bottle was fitted

with an airtight screw cap to prevent gas leaks.

After 48 h, volatile aldehyde trapped by the aldehyde-absorbing reagent MBTH was determined. A 3-ml aliquot of MBTH was collected from each bottle, put into a test tube containing 2.5 ml of 0.23% (wt/vol) ferric chloride solution, and incubated for 10 min. We then added

20,000 accessions) is a rich source of resistance to BPH.

An insect-feeding test on bromocresol-treated filter paper was also

with an airtight screw cap to prevent gas leaks. After 48 h, volatile aldehyde trapped by the aldehyde-absorbing reagent MBTH was determined. A 3-ml aliquot of MBTH was collected from each bottle, put into a test tube containing 2.5 ml of 0.23% (wt/vol) ferric chloride solution, and incubated for 10 min. We then added

conducted. Insect feeding was judged by the amount of honeydew deposited by a female in 24 h on resistant cultivars Hinga, Kappe, Dhouri 1043, Dhouri 1163, Jaybay Rang, Khatia Pati, Kanak, Ganja Kali, Hiranakhi, and EB 17. Feeding rate was 0.17-65 mm² per female in 24 h, which was much lower than the 173-235 mm² per female feeding on TN1. On the resistant check PTB33, the rate was 49 mm² per female.

Hinga 435 and Dhouri 1043 had low plant damage scores and feeding rates of 65 and 53 mm² per female, respectively, suggesting that the genotypes have the ability to maintain vigor at those feeding rates. However, no correlation between plant damage score and feeding rate on Minga 435 and Dhouri 1043 was observed. ■

2.5 ml of absolute acetone to the tube and closed it with a tightly fitting cork. After 30 min, the absorbance of the reaction mixture was read at 635 nm. Formaldehyde solutions were used as standards.

The results showed that tissues from previously submerged plants released 0-8 times more volatile aldehydes than tissues from nonsubmerged plants.

Amount of volatile aldehydes produced by 70-d-old rice plants after 6 d submergence.

Variety	Survival (%) ^a	Volatile aldehydes produced (ml gas/100 g)		
		Submerged (control)	Submerged for 6 d	Increase over control ^b (%)
<i>Submergence-tolerant</i>				
FR13A (check)	80	16.0	21.0	5.0 (31)
Sabita	75	9.0	14.0	5.0 (55)
<i>Moderately submergence-tolerant</i>				
Sureh	65	4.1	17.0	12.9 (309)
Patnai 23	60	4.3	4.5	0.2 (4)
Jogen	45	4.3	21.4	17.1 (396)
Mahsuri	45	18.4	28.8	10.4 (56)
<i>Submergence-susceptible</i>				
Pankaj	40	4.0	17.0	13.0 (329)
Swarnadhan	35	18.4	32.1	13.7 (75)
Biraj	35	13.3	21.2	7.9 (59)
IR42 (check)	25	5.4	42.5	37.1 (687)
Mean	50	9.7	22.0	12.2
SE	5.5	1.9	3.1	3.0
LSD (0.05)	28	9.5	16.1	15.5

^aData taken after 12 d complete submergence at 60 DAT. ^bFigures in parentheses are percentages.